

SHORT COMMUNICATION

ANTIBODIES TO NEWCASTLE AND INFECTIOUS BURSAL DISEASES IN CHICKS FROM SOME COMMERCIAL HATCHERIES IN NIGERIA

Wakawa, A.M.¹, Sami, F.A.¹, Aliyu, H.B.² and Talba, A.M.².

¹Department of Veterinary Medicine, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria

²Veterinary Teaching Hospital, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

A survey was conducted to determine the presence of antibodies to Newcastle disease (ND) and infectious bursal disease (IBD) in chicks purchased from some commercial hatcheries in Nigeria. Sera were collected from 1 to 3 day-old chicks, selected at random from 32 batches of 20 chicks each from 12 commercial hatcheries. The presence of antibodies to ND and IBD were determined by haemagglutination inhibition (HI) and agar gel immunodiffusion (AGID) techniques, respectively. Of the 640 sera assayed, 290 (45.3%) were positive for ND antibodies with a mean antibody titre of $4.6 \pm 0.3 \log_2$, while 139 (21.7%) were positive for antibodies to IBD. The results suggested that these chicks were not adequately equipped to withstand natural infection with ND and IBD viruses. It was recommended that hatcheries should vaccinate their breeder flocks against ND and IBD so that maternal antibodies may be transferred to chicks via the egg yolk, to protect them against the diseases during their early stages.

KEY WORDS: antibodies, chicks, hatcheries, infectious bursal disease, Newcastle disease,

INTRODUCTION

Newcastle disease (ND) and Infectious bursal disease (IBD) continue to be serious economic threats to the poultry industry in Nigeria (Ohore *et al.*, 2002; Abdu *et al.*, 2007). ND is a highly contagious, generalised viral disease of domestic poultry and wild birds (Al-Garib *et al.*, 2003). It is worldwide in distribution, and is caused by *Paramyxovirus*, a member of the family *Paramyxoviridae*. IBD, also known as Gumboro disease, is an acute and highly contagious viral disease of immature chickens, caused by a virus that is a member of the genus *Avibirnavirus* of the family *Birnaviridae*, characterized by destruction of the lymphocytes in the bursa of Fabricius and to a lesser extent in other lymphoid organs (Lukhert and Saif, 2003; Abdu *et al.*, 2007). The disease is a major problem in concentrated poultry production areas throughout the world. Affected chickens have reduced antibody response to vaccinations, strong post-vaccinal reactions, and increased susceptibility to concurrent or secondary infections (Baxendale, 1981; Lukhert and Saif, 1997). Once established in a poultry rearing area, the virus infection may occur in subsequent flocks if proper disinfection and husbandry conditions are not observed. IBD vaccines are in use throughout the world but all have a common problem i.e. when is the best time (age) to vaccinate? If live IBD vaccine is administered to chickens that have high level of maternally-derived antibodies (MDA), the vaccine will be neutralized by these antibodies. As a result the vaccine will not induce protection. The transfers of passive immunity in the form of MDA against ND and IBD from parent stock to chicks have been reported (Higgins, 1971; Saidu *et al.*, 2006b). The MDA may persist in chicks for up to 6 or 7 weeks, and such chicks do not develop bursal lesions initially when challenged, but may after 5 weeks or so (Baxendale, 1981). On the other hand, one does not want to wait too long before vaccinating as this will leave the flock unprotected against early challenge (Tsai *et al.*, 1995). As a consequence, different vaccination schedules have been recommended in practice to farmers by commercial hatcheries, veterinary practitioners and other animal health workers in Nigeria. Studies on ND and IBD antibodies have previously been conducted in Nigeria (Oyeduntan and Durojaiye, 1999). Retrospective analyses of ND and IBD outbreaks conducted by Sa'idu *et al.* (2006a) and Mbuko *et al.* (2010), respectively, indicated prevalences of 32.3% and 7.26%, respectively, and recent increases in frequency of ND and IBD cases in chicks being presented to the Avian Clinic, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria. The present study is to complement earlier studies particularly since there has been observable increase in ND and IBD cases in Zaria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Survey Population

A total of 640 blood samples were collected from chicks selected at random, from 32 batches of chicks purchased by poultry farmers from some commercial hatcheries located in Ibadan, Abeokuta, Jos, Ilorin, Kaduna and Shika in Nigeria,. Twenty samples were collected per batch irrespective of flock size. The age of the chicks ranged between 1 and 3-day-old. The samples were mostly collected between March and May, in 2009, 2010 and 2011, which coincide with the period of poultry farm restocking in Nigeria.

Preparation of Sera

One milliliter of whole blood was collected from each chick directly from the heart using insulin syringes and 26G needles. The blood was allowed to clot at room temperature. Sera were separated by centrifugation at about 447.2 xg for 5 minutes. The sera were stored in the refrigerator until used.

Screening For Newcastle Disease Antibodies

Preparation of 1% Red Blood Cells

Two ml of blood was collected from 1-3 day-old chicks that were negative for ND and IBD antibodies, and pooled in an equal volume of Alsever's anticoagulant solution. Cells were washed three times in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (pH 7.2) by centrifuging at 447.2 xg for 5 minutes. One percent red blood cell (RBC) (packed cell v/v) suspension was made by adding 99 ml of PBS to 1ml of washed RBC.

Detection of Newcastle Disease Antibodies

The titre of ND vaccine virus (La Sota strain) obtained from the National Veterinary Research Institute (NVRI), Vom, Nigeria, was first determined by Haemagglutination test (HA) as previously described (OIE, 2004) and used as the antigen. Antibodies to ND were detected by the Haemagglutination inhibition (HI) test as previously described (OIE, 2004). Serial dilutions of 25 µl of each serum sample were carried out in microtitre plates using PBS as diluents. Each volume of serum was reacted with 4HA units of the ND vaccine antigen for 30 minutes at room temperature (25°C). About 25 µl of the 1% washed chicken erythrocytes, dispensed into every well including the control wells were used as an indicator. Reaction was allowed to occur at room temperature for 30 minutes after which the results were read. The HI titre was the highest dilution of serum causing complete inhibition of 4 HAU of antigen. The agglutination was assessed by tilting the plates. Only those wells in which the RBCs streamed at the same rate as the control wells were considered to show inhibition. The validity of the test was assessed against a negative control serum, which gave a titre $>4 \log_2$ when and a positive control serum for which the titre was $>12 \log_2$.

Screening For Antibodies To Infectious Bursal Disease

Preparation of Infectious Bursal Disease Antigen

Bursae of Fabricius were harvested from cases of IBD at Avian Clinic, Ahmadu Bello University Veterinary Teaching Hospital, Zaria, Nigeria, macerated and homogenized in a tissue grinder, and centrifuged at about 447.2 xg for 5 minutes. The supernatant which serve as the bursal tissue antigen (crude antigen) was collected and stored at -4°C until used.

Detecting The Presence of Antibodies To Infectious Bursal Disease

Antibodies to IBD in the sera were determined by agar gel immunodiffusion (AGID) test as previously described (OIE, 2004). Briefly, 5 mm wells were made on agar gel in the petri dishes. The central wells were filled with 25 µl of the IBD homogenized bursal tissue antigen, while the peripheral wells were filled each with 25 µl of sera. The set up was incubated at 37°C. The results were first read at 24-36 hours and finally read at 72 hours. The appearance of specific precipitin lines was taken as the indicator of a positive antibody reaction.

Controls

The controls consisted of hyper-immune sera prepared in chickens after two successive inoculations with known positive antigens of ND and IBD. While chickens known to be free from ND and IBD antibodies (unvaccinated) were used as negative controls.

Data Analysis

The data generated were reduced into a table. The prevalences of ND and IBD were expressed in percentages, while the mean \pm standard error (SE) of ND antibody titres was calculated.

RESULTS

A total of 640 samples were examined for antibodies, out of which 290 (45.3%) were positive for ND antibodies, while 139 (21.7%) were positive for antibodies to IBD. Antibodies to both ND and IBD were not detected in sera obtained from flocks of 2 hatcheries, while antibodies to IBD alone were not detected in sera obtained from flocks of 5 hatcheries. Antibodies to ND were detected in chicks from 10 (83.3%) of the 12 hatcheries. The mean ND antibody titre for all the samples was $4.6 \pm 0.3 \log_2$, while chicks with antibodies to IBD were detected in 7(58.3%) of the hatcheries. However, the antibody titre for IBD was not determined in view of the qualitative nature of the test (Table 1).

Table 1. Distribution of antibodies to Newcastle and Infectious bursal diseases in chicks from some commercial hatcheries in Nigeria

Sampled hatchery	Location	No of batches sampled	Sample size	No. positive for antibodies to IBD (%)	No. positive for ND antibodies (%)	Mean ND antibody titre \pm SE (\log_2)
Hatchery I	Ibadan	4	80	22 (27.5)	40 (50.0)	6.8 ± 0.4
Hatchery II	Ibadan	2	40	13 (32.5)	32 (80.0)	5.2 ± 0.1
Hatchery III	Ibadan	3	60	0	28 (46.7)	5.1 ± 0.1
Hatchery IV	Ibadan	3	60	32 (53.3)	36 (60.0)	4.3 ± 0.3
Hatchery V	Ibadan	2	40	10 (25.0)	23 (57.5)	6.4 ± 0.4
Hatchery VI	Abeokuta	4	80	32 (40.0)	52 (65.0)	6.2 ± 0.1
Hatchery VII	Abeokuta	3	60	16 (26.7)	34 (56.7)	4.2 ± 0.2
Hatchery VIII	Jos	2	40	0	20 (50.0)	5.4 ± 0.2
Hatchery IX	Jos	1	20	0	0	0
Hatchery X	Ilorin	4	80	14 (17.5)	10 (50)	5.2 ± 0.1
Hatchery XI	Kaduna	2	40	0	15 (37.5)	6.4 ± 0.3
Hatchery XII	Shika	2	40	0	0	0
		32	640	139 (21.7%)	290 (45.3%)	4.6 ± 0.3

ND: Newcastle disease, IBD: Infectious Bursal Disease

DISCUSSION

Given that ND is endemic in Nigeria, the prevalence determined implied inadequate protection of commercial chicks population against ND. It is also important to note that the overall mean of $4.6 \pm 0.3 \log_2$ which was marginal, may not be enough to provide adequate protection against a highly virulent strain of ND virus in the event of subsequent exposure to natural infection, even though the recommended minimum protective antibody titre against ND is $4 \log_2$ (OIE, 2004; Saidu *et al.*, 2006b). The finding that 3 batches of chicks were completely negative for ND antibodies further complement those of Adene and Njoku (1979) who reported low ND antibody prevalence and titres for imported day-old exotic chicks in Nigeria. It is clear therefore that the response of these chicks to devastating effects of natural infection with virulent ND virus might be severe (Abdu and Garba, 1989; Abdu *et al.*, 2007).

The results obtained for MDA in chicks suggests that the overall protection level against natural IBD virus infection may also be grossly inadequate (Geidam *et al.*, 2008), even though the MDA titres were not expressed. It is also worrisome to observe that 3 batches of chicks from 2 of the 12 hatcheries were negative for both ND and IBD antibodies. A possible explanation to this might be; even with high uniform titred breeder flocks, it is possible that 10% of the chicks may not carry any antibodies. Even more compelling is that when the breeder flock titres become less than adequate, the number of chicks without antibodies might increase dramatically (Sai'du *et al.*, 2006b). For example, in a flock of 12,000 chicks, it is possible to have 1, 200 or more chicks without any maternal antibodies to protect them against the two diseases. This implied that the chicks in the aforementioned batches were ill-equipped to withstand the destructive effects of the pantrophic ND and lymphotropic IBD viruses, and were at great risk of suffering from the diseases in the event of exposure to field strains of the viruses. The farmer may experience heavy economic losses if natural outbreaks of the diseases eventually occur in these birds. Consequently different vaccination schedules have been recommended in practice. Despite these vaccination schedules, outbreaks are still been recorded.. (Wisniewska and Stosik, 1999).

Studies conducted by Partadiredja *et al* (1979) showed that maternal antibody levels to ND in one-day-old chicks were related to the titres of antibody in the dams. Maternal antibody titres of chicks originated from breeder flocks that were vaccinated with oil-emulsion vaccine remained high for all hatcheries (Abdu and Garba, 1989). Therefore, for chicks to be protected against early infection with ND and IBD viruses, breeders must be vaccinated against these diseases (Abdu *et al*, 2007; Geidam *et al.*, 2008)). Hyperimmunizing breeders with inactivated ND and IBD vaccines will achieve protection against the diseases. The breeders would develop high levels of antibodies, which would be transmitted via the yolk to the progeny chicks in form of MDA, and these could protect the chicks against early natural infection with IBD virus, although the duration of parental immunity could vary in the progeny, and outbreaks have been reported at different stages of the progeny (Wyeth and Cullen, 1976).

The results of this study suggest that a large proportion of chicks population from some of the hatcheries may not be adequately protected against ND and IBD. A lot of attempts need to be made to reduce the heavy economic losses incurred due to these diseases by farmers. It is highly recommended that breeders should be vaccinated against the diseases in order to transfer MDA to chicks. Hatcheries should endeavour to vaccinate newly-hatched chicks against ND before releasing them to farmers. Farmers on the other hand, should routinely check the immunological status of their chicks against ND and IBD as soon as they purchase chicks, especially in areas where the facility exist; as this might significantly assist in designing a vaccination programme for their flocks against the diseases.

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Corresponding author

Wakawa, A.M

Department of Veterinary Medicine, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria

E-mail: asmwakawa@yahoo.com